

BRAIN INFECTION OF OTIC ORIGIN, WITH REPORT OF FIVE CASES.*

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That every case of suppurating ear is a menace to the owner is well illustrated in the series of five cases which I have seen in the past year, and wish to report to-day.

These cases are interesting. (1) From the slight symptoms present up to within a few hours of the time of operation; (2) in every case we were able to trace the origin of infection to a lesion in the middle ear, in three of the operated cases, at the time of the operation, and in the two non-operative fatal cases at a subsequent post-mortem.

The portion of the brain most likely to be involved from middle ear infection depends often upon the manner in which the infection occurs. My experience has been that when it occurs by direct continuity, the temporo-sphenoidal lobe is most often the site of the abscess. When the extension is through the labyrinth, the abscess is most often on the anterior aspect of the cerebellum for the abscess is most often found adjacent to the infected bone area.

Diagnosis: Since abscess of the brain of otic origin is a secondary, and not a primary disease, the problem of diagnosis is often masked by the primary disease, or some of its complications. Quite a large extra-dural abscess may be present with little or no symptoms. Cerebral abscess of otic origin, being an acute infection, the time is generally too short for the pathognomonic eye symptoms to develop, as is the case in tumors of the brain, hence the absence of optic neuritis does not exclude cerebral abscess.

Paralysis is of importance in helping to locate the abscess, since the lesion must lie in the zone of inflammatory tissue, near the center for the muscles involved.

The section through this wet specimen shows the most usual site of the abscess when of otic origin.

The section through the pons is at the site of the aqueduct of Sylvius. Now, it is at this point that the third nerve has its deep origin on either side of the aqueduct of Sylvius, and passes out on the side of the red nuclei, just a little anterior to the aqueduct.

This shows clearly how an abscess of the temporo-sphenoidal

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lobe would soon exert pressure on the deep origin of the third nerve, causing paralysis of the group of muscles controlled by this nerve, which is one of the earliest symptoms of a temporo-sphenoidal abscess.

Paralysis of the third nerve on the side of the suspected abscess is an important diagnostic symptom. The paralysis is rarely complete. If the pupil on the side of the suspected abscess fails to respond to light, the diagnosis is rendered more certain. The mental symptoms may simulate those of opium poisoning, and when met with in the presence of a purulent otitis media, must always arouse suspicion of brain complications.

With a temperature nearly normal or slightly sub-normal a slow pulse, slow respiration, slow cerebation, and want of sustained attention, mental obscuration, and a tendency to doze even when talking, all point strongly to a cerebral abscess.

When the abscess is in the cerebellum, the respirations are much slower than when it is in the temporo-sphenoidal lobe, and is more apt to be irregular, and of the Cheyne-Stokes character. In cerebellar abscess with pressure on the pons, respiration may cease some little time before the heart stops.

Treatment: An abscess of the brain must be dealt with surgically, the same as an abscess in any other part of the body. Once the diagnosis is made and the quicker the abscess is evacuated, the better the prognosis.

The incision should be planned so as to provide for free evacuation and drainage afterwards. I feel that these operations should consume as little time as possible, when once the brain is exposed.

When the abscess to be opened is situated some distance from the dura, I prefer a perfectly sharp, long "Weis" cataract knife for making the incision through the intervening brain substance. The blade is so sharp that it readily pierces a tough capsule, and is so thin, that the minimum amount of trauma is produced. Once the abscess is located, it can be more freely opened by means of a fine artery forceps.

The abscess should be adjacent to the infective bone area, and the incision should be made in this direction.

Case 1: Mr. C., aged 63, was seen March 4, 1914, by Dr. J. O. Blackerby, of Montgomery, Ohio, with the following history: After an exposure during one of the recent blizzards, he complained of some soreness in the neck and back of the right ear, but it was not of sufficient severity to cause him to consult his family physician, and he continued at his work, thinking the trouble was only due to

a cold and would soon pass off. At no time was there any discharge from the ear.

When I saw the case the following day, there was marked edema of the tissue over the mastoid, and the swelling extended into the neck, suggesting the presence of a Bezold abscess. At the first glance, the appearance of the mastoid with no discharge from the ear, suggested a possible furunculosis of the auditory canal. Examination showed the canal to be normal, and the middle ear dry, but some evidence of an old chronic non-inflammatory middle ear trouble. Temperature, 102° F., and considerable pain complained of in the neck along the tendons of the sterno-cleido-mastoid muscle, with some tenderness at the tip, a diagnostic point in extra-dural abscess.

To my surprise no pus was encountered in my incision over the mastoid, and not until the entire tip was exposed was the real seat of the trouble encountered. In the under surface of the mastoid tip there was a perforation about the size of a lead pencil, which opened into a large abscess at the tip. The pus had traveled along the tendons of the sterno-cleido-mastoid and produced a typical Bezold's abscess, containing several ounces of thick, creamy pus. While the outer surface of the mastoid was intact, the entire pneumatic process was one mass of necrosed cells and pus. The lateral sinus was exposed and found covered with granulations, while a large opening in the tegmen tympani communicated directly with the dura, through which quite a quantity of extra-dural pus escaped when the opening was enlarged and the dura depressed.

The bone destruction was quite extensive, and a strange feature of the case was that with all this destruction and pus in the mastoid, there were no symptoms of the process in the middle ear. This absence of middle ear suppuration was explained by the presence of firm granulations in the attic completely shutting off communication with the middle ear. A radical mastoid had to be done and the patient made a satisfactory recovery. The Bezold's abscess had to be opened low down in the neck and drained. The clinical symptoms were so slight that the patient refused to consult his family physician till the day before he was operated upon.

Case 2: John N., a large, well-developed boy, 15 years of age, was seen in consultation with Dr. John R. Murnan and Dr. R. W. Bledsoe, of Covington, Ky., March 15, 1915. He gave the following history: Six weeks ago, following an exposure, he complained of pain in the left ear. He consulted his family physician, Dr. Murnan, of Covington, Ky. The doctor ordered a hot boracic acid douche

and gave him a laxative. The next day the ear began to discharge and the pain ceased. Under this treatment the discharge gradually lessened, and in about ten days ceased and the parents considered the ear well. After remaining dry for a week the discharge suddenly began again and has continued ever since, in spite of a free myringotomy by Dr. Bledsoe. No pain was complained of over the mastoid, and at no time was there swelling or any external symptoms of the inflamed mastoid. About the only pain complained of was located over the left temporal region and the left frontal sinus. Examination of the frontal sinuses was negative, yet the symptom simulated a violent sinusitis. The pain was worse at night. For the past two weeks it has been almost impossible to get his bowels moved, and expulsive vomiting, which was present, was attributed to the drugs used to overcome the constipation, which was most pronounced. The boy was able to be up and about, and was in Dr. Bledsoe's office for treatment, March 14, 1914. In the afternoon, the following day, March 15, the boy suddenly had a convulsion and became unconscious. I saw him that evening for the first time in consultation. The patient was profoundly unconscious. The left external canal was full of mucus-like pus. There was a free opening in the anterior portion of the drum, a slight sagging of the superior-posterior wall of the canal near the drum. There was a slight dropping of the left eye-lid, and the eye turned to affected side. The pupil of the left eye was dilated and failed to respond to light. The right pupil was normal, but sluggish. A diagnosis of localized acute meningitis was made, and opening and drainage of the mastoid advised. Before the patient could be taken to the hospital, the symptoms grew rapidly worse, and the patient died early the next morning without having regained consciousness.

We were fortunate in getting a post-mortem in this case. We found the petrous portion of the left temporal bone much darker than the right, with several areas of roughened bone, showing the point of meningeal infection. The entire petrous portion of the bone was filled with pus and broken-down bone cells. Since, for the past week, the pain complained of was over the left temporal region, extending up over the left frontal, this cavity was opened and found to be normal. The tegmen tympani was also eroded. The left temporal lobe was much discolored but no abscess was present, but a local, well-defined acute meningitis of the left temporal lobe was present, which accounted for the intra-cranial symptoms; expulsive vomiting, obstinate constipation, Jackson's epileptic seizures and paralysis of the third nerve.

Section through brain showing the most frequent location of abscess of otic origin.

Case 3: John R., aged 6 years, was seen in consultation with Dr. Bledsoe, July 3, 1914. He gives the following history: Three weeks ago the patient had symptoms of mastoid involvement following a discharging ear of recent origin. As there was evidence of pus under the soft tissue over the infected ear, the family physician incised same and evacuated a sub-periosteal abscess.

The ear continued to discharge and two weeks later Dr. Bledsoe did a simple mastoid operation.

The patient did well for one week, when he developed symptoms of cerebral complications.

When I saw the case, the child was comatose, with slow pulse, slow respirations, pupils widely dilated, and the eye on the side of the lesion turned outward.

A diagnosis of temporo-sphenoidal abscess was made, and an unfavorable prognosis given. Operation was immediately decided upon.

After removing a button of bone from the temporal region, one inch above and slightly in front of the external canal (auditory), there was pronounced bulging of the dura with no pulsation and a fluctuating sensation on palpation.

A crucial incision was made in the dura, and the underlying brain substance exposed.

The brain seemed softened, but no evidence of abscess was present at this point.

A fine Weis cataract knife was passed in about one and one-half inches downwards and forwards, when it encountered an enormously enlarged encysted abscess of the temporo-sphenoidal lobe. The pus was under such tension, that when incised it spurted fully three inches above the wound. Many bubbles of gas escaped with an audible noise, during the discharge. The wound was enlarged with artery forceps, inserted closed, and then opened. Fully four or five ounces of most foul-smelling pus was evacuated. The wound was packed with gauze and the dura sutured.

The pulse, which was only fifty before the incision, immediately arose to 115, and the pupils became active, and by the following morning the paralysis had disappeared, and consciousness had returned.

There was considerable hernia cerebri for a week or two, as the intervening brain substance seemed almost liquid. However, by firmly bandaging the wound each day, this gradually subsided, and the little patient made a rapid convalescence, and now seems entirely recovered, almost a year after the abscess was evacuated.

Case 4: Leroy B., age 7, was first seen October 10, 1914, having been referred by Dr. Larkin, of Hillsboro, Ohio. He gave the following history: In December, 1913, he was operated upon for abscess of the right ear by another surgeon, but the wound back of the ear has never healed. It continued to discharge a very foul-smelling pus, and it was this discharge and foul smell that caused them to seek relief.

Some five or six weeks before, the child had had what the mother called a convulsion, lasting for about fifteen minutes.

At times the discharge would almost cease, when the child would become restless and complain of pain over the ear and the corresponding frontal sinus. There would then be a free discharge of foul-smelling pus, when all of the symptoms would disappear. The child seemed normal in every other way and was a regular attendant at school. There were absolutely no symptoms of brain infection.

The external ear was dry, the drum normal in appearance and hearing about normal.

Thinking that we simply had a sinus to deal with, and possibly an area of necrosed bone that needed curetting, an anesthetic was given and the wound opened.

In opening a mastoid wound for the second time, where I have not done the original operation, I make it a rule to go some distance outside of the original incision, so if dura or sinus have been exposed, there is less danger of wounding the same. The wisdom of this precaution was well illustrated in this case. To my surprise, I found that neither the antrum nor a single mastoid cell had been opened, but that a button of bone about the size of a silver half-dollar had been removed from the temporal bone. Through this bone-opening there was a tense, bulging, nonpulsating dura protruding. I opened the antrum and found evidence of an old mastoid inflammation, but no pus.

Feeling certain that we were now dealing with a temporo-sphenoidal abscess, the bone-opening was enlarged slightly downwards, so as to get better drainage.

A thin Weis cataract knife was then passed downwards and forwards, keeping about half an inch from the inner wall of the skull.

About one inch from the opening a tense yielding mass was encountered. Slight pressure on the knife caused it to enter an abscess from which pus gushed with such force as to cover the hand holding the knife. Artery forceps were inserted along the blade of the knife, and opened, when fully four ounces of most offensive

pus was evacuated. There seemed to be much gas in the discharge, which at times, would come away with quite a bubbling sound.

The cavity was washed out with a normal saline solution and packed with gauze.

Since there was no other source of the diffuse discharge which had been complained of for months, I feel certain that it all came from the encysted abscess which would leak externally when the pressure became too great. This leakage was no doubt the salvation of this little patient.

We were not troubled with hernia cerebri, as the dura, pia and arachnoid were firmly bound together, and as small an incision as was compatible with proper drainage was made.

The child made a rapid convalescence. He seems to be entirely well now, and has taken up his school work once more.

Case 5: John S., age about 35, a strong, powerfully built man, was brought to the Cincinnati Hospital about midnight, November 22, 1914. He was in a profoundly comatose condition and no history was obtainable.

Dr. Hinnan saw the case first, and I was asked to see him in consultation the following morning.

I asked Dr. Baer, the neurologist, to see the case also.

We found the patient profoundly unconscious, pupils contracted, and not responsive to light, corneal reflexes abolished. Temperature 99, pulse 190, respirations stertorous, examination of urine negative.

Over the right mastoid there was an old scar, of a former mastoid operation, and there was pus in the right external auditory canal.

An immediate operation was decided upon, and the patient prepared for the same. A few moments after being placed on the operating table, and before the operation could be begun, the pupils suddenly dilated, respirations stopped, and, in spite of artificial respiration and the use of the pulmotor, the heart stopped.

I quickly removed the necrotic mastoid cells and made an opening through the tegmen tympani, incised the dura and opened into a large temporo-sphenoidal abscess.

From the amount of cerebral fluid that came away with the pus, I am satisfied the sudden torpor that came on was due to the abscess bursting into the lateral ventricle on that side.

These five cases of brain infection have been seen in the past year, and, in every case, we were able to demonstrate positively that a suppurating middle ear was the direct cause of the brain infection.

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